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Challenges and Coping Mechanisms of Teachers Teaching Learners with Special Needs

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Abstract

This study explores the foundation of education and its role in addressing the diverse needs of learners, particularly those with special needs, in a regular classroom setting. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected from 150 teachers using researcher-made questionnaires. The respondents were selected through random sampling to ensure a representative sample. The study aimed to validate the development of educational strategies for learners with special needs. The findings highlight the necessity of Special Education Teachers in every school and the provision of adequate resources to support these learners. A significant issue identified was the lack of parental support, attributed to insufficient knowledge among both teachers and parents in handling learners with special needs. This lack of support at home emerged as a major challenge, adversely affecting teachers' coping mechanisms and, consequently, their teaching performance. Recommendations based on the study's conclusions include: (1) providing teachers with seminars and training on Special and Inclusive Education; (2) encouraging parental and community involvement in supporting children's education; (3) advocating for curriculum planners to incorporate Special and Inclusive Education into the Basic Education goals; (4) fostering a supportive and trusting workplace culture within schools; and (5) suggesting future research to expand on these findings and explore additional variables related to Special and Inclusive Education.

Keywords: *diverse needs of learners, special education teachers, challenges, coping mechanisms*

Introduction

Education is merely a foundation of all aspects of educating the learners. Educating the learners has different levels of developmental knowledge as pertain to the skills, characteristics, and mode of learning delivery. Inclusion is a fundamental principle in education that aims to provide learners with special needs the opportunity to receive education in regular education classrooms alongside their typically developing peers. It is a practice rooted in the belief that every student, regardless of their abilities or disabilities, has the right to access quality education in the least restrictive environment. Inclusion supports the academic progress of learners with special needs, fosters social integration, promotes diversity, and prepares students for an inclusive society.

The challenges encountered by the teachers and parent has been heard and given emphasis by the government that learners with disabilities have the right to educate as stipulated in Republic Act (RA) 11050, which was signed by President Rodrigo Roa Duterte in Metro Manila last July 26, 2021, stated that no learners shall be denied admission based on their disabilities. The law provides that all public or private schools ensure equitable access to quality education for every learner with disabilities. According to the law, it shall include the provision of assistive devices, facilities, and infrastructure in the admission process and other forms of reasonable accommodation.

While the concept of inclusion has gained widespread recognition and support, its effective implementation poses significant challenges for educators. This study explores the challenges teachers face in facilitating the inclusion of learners with special needs into the regular education classroom. By understanding these challenges, can identify the barriers that hinder successful inclusion and work towards developing strategies to overcome them.

One of the key challenges that educators encounter is the need to provide appropriate support and accommodations to meet the diverse learning needs of learners with special needs. Each student possesses unique abilities, learning styles, and individualized requirements, making it crucial for educators to differentiate instruction and create inclusive learning environments that cater to these needs. Additionally, managing behavioral issues and ensuring the social integration of learners with special needs can be complex tasks that require specialized skills and knowledge.

Another challenge is the limited training and professional development opportunities available to educators in the context of inclusive education. Educators need comprehensive training that equips them with the necessary strategies and resources to effectively address the diverse needs of learners with special needs in the regular education classroom. Without proper support and guidance, teachers may feel ill-prepared to handle the complexities associated with inclusive education, leading to potential gaps in educational experiences for learners with special needs.

The social dynamics within the regular education classroom also present challenges. Students with special needs may face stigmatization, isolation, or a lack of acceptance from their typically developing peers, hindering their social integration and overall well-being. Educators must address these issues through the promotion of positive attitudes, empathy, and inclusive classroom cultures.

Understanding the challenges faced by educators in facilitating the inclusion of learners with special needs is essential for the development of effective strategies and interventions. By identifying these challenges, policymakers, administrators, and educators can work collaboratively to implement sustainable practices that support the successful inclusion of learners with special needs in regular education classrooms. The concern of learners with special needs education or with disabilities shall be accorded services and reasonable accommodation based on the individualized education plan (IEP) and shall have the right to avail of the appropriate support and related services.

The purpose of this study was to examine the specific challenges faced by teachers in the facilitation of inclusion, investigate their impact on learners with special needs and their typically developing peers, and explore strategies and interventions that can address these challenges. The findings from this study contribute to the existing knowledge base, inform educational policies, and provide practical recommendations to support educators in their efforts to create inclusive and equitable learning environments for all students.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to determine the challenges and coping mechanisms of teachers teaching learners with special needs that regulate classes in regular education classrooms of the 17 schools of North II District, Division of Iligan City. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of challenges by the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms in terms of:
 - 1.1 concentration factor on teaching facilitation;
 - 1.2 teacher struggles with learners with special needs;
 - 1.3 behavioral transformations of learners with special needs;
 - 1.4 mental health awareness; and
 - 1.5 assistance at home?
2. What is the coping mechanism of the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' coping mechanisms and the challenges of teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms?
4. Which of the respondents' challenges of teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms best predict teachers' coping mechanisms?
5. What action plan can be classified based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

This section deals with the series of procedures and methods that involve the teaching and learning of learners with special needs in education. It also discusses the research design, research environment, respondents, sampling procedures, research instruments and their validity, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design in which information was collected without changing the subject. This was descriptive since the study described the challenges in teaching learners with special needs in terms of concentration factor on teaching facilitation, teacher struggles in learners with special needs, behavioral transformations of learners with special needs, mental health awareness at school, and assistance at home and respondents' coping mechanisms. It was a correlational design since the study tried to investigate the relationship between the respondents' coping mechanisms and the challenges in teaching learners with special needs in the 17 schools of North II District, Division of Iligan City, during the School Year 2022-2023.

Participants

The study has been validated based on the development of catering to learners with special needs of education in the regular classroom. The respondents were rated using the researcher-made questionnaires. The study's respondents were 150 teachers. Random sampling was used in this study to identify the number of desired characteristics that suited the study's purpose. The schools were given questionnaires according to the number of teachers in that school. These are the number of respondents per school:

Table 1. *Respondents of the study*

<i>Name Of School</i>	<i>Total Number of Teachers</i>	<i>Actual Number of Respondents</i>
Iligan City East National High School	130	50
Kiwalan National High School	31	20
Kiwalan Elementary School	40	20
Mainit High School	11	5
Kapisahan Integrated School	9	5
Caribao Elementary School	4	4
Echavez Elementary School	14	10

Acmac Elementary School	10	4
Sultan Mamarinta Panandigan Integrated School	24	15
Venancio Siarza Memorial Elementary School	3	3
Benito S. Ong Elementary School	8	3
Sardab Elementary School	6	2
Ampucao Elementary School	8	3
Rebucon Elementary School	5	2
Pudog Elementary School	2	2
Lower Mainit Elementary School	2	2
TOTAL	307	150

Instruments

In this study, the researcher-made used as an instrument. The questionnaire was piloted in the nearest school from another district which is North I, particularly at The Dalipuga Central School. The Questionnaire consisted of 2 parts for the teachers. Part I was the level of challenges encountered; Part II was the academic performance of the learners with special needs in education. The researcher-made questionnaires were composed of 30 questions that were answered by the teachers using the 4-likert scale Strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree.

Procedure

The researchers secured permission for the conduct of the research from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent from the selected district as the respondents of the study. The approved letter request was forwarded to the Public Schools District Supervisor for information and instruction during the distribution of questionnaires to the respective respondent schools. Thus, the researchers proceeded to the schools to administer the questionnaires to the respective school heads and teachers' respondents.

Statistical Treatment

The data were gathered, summarized, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted from the actual data needed and information coming from the schools' readiness respondents. The statistical techniques were used in answering the questionnaires as presented.

Frequency and Percentage. Frequency and percentage were used to identify the academic performance of the learners.

Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation. Weighted mean and standard deviation are used here to determine the level of challenges of teaching learners with special needs education.

Pearson Product of-Moment Correlation Coefficient. Pearson product-moment of correlation coefficient was used in problem 5, to determine the significant relationship between the challenges encountered by learners with special needs and learners without special needs in addressing effective teaching strategies.

All the computations were computed using the electronic Statistics Software of an accredited statistician.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzes and interprets the data collected by the researchers to solve the issues in the study.

Problem 1: What is the extent of challenges by the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms in terms of concentration factor on teaching facilitation, teacher struggles in learners with special needs, behavioral transformations of learners with special needs, assistance at school, and assistance at home?

Table 2. *Concentration Factor on Teaching Facilitation*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I get distracted whenever I see learners with special needs in education.	2.39	±	1.00	Disagree
2. I have felt discomfort and confusion when there is/are learners with special needs in education.	2.44	±	0.93	Disagree
3. I have found learners with disabilities uninterested in facilitating their learning progress.	2.43	±	0.94	Disagree
4. I cannot focus on involving/facilitating learners with special needs education in a regular education classroom.	2.31	±	0.87	Disagree
5. During moments when learners with special educational needs experience tantrums, I find it effortless to redirect my focus towards engaging activities such as gardening or farming, or even reviewing the notebooks of other learners. This not only allows me to effectively manage the situation but also ensures that I maintain a productive and nurturing learning environment	2.67	±	0.77	Agree
6. I found it challenging to facilitate sessions for learners with special educational needs within the school or community.	2.97	±	0.75	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.54	±	0.64	Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

Table 2 presents the extent of challenges by the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms in terms of concentration factor on teaching facilitation. The table includes 6 statements, and the respondents were questioned to rate their level of agreement using a scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). The total measure of respondents' concentration factor in teaching learners with special needs was 2.54, indicating that the respondents had overall agreed with the statements.

The result showed that fewer teachers get distracted whenever they see learners with special needs education and in contrast, the majority of teachers found it challenging to facilitate sessions for learners with special educational needs within the school or community. These teachers under the lowest mean could sometimes find difficult, working with these children doesn't go one way and they have to work with a lot of other things also so keep working and thinking a lot out of the box and they should make another worksheet for them. Many of these teachers are saying that motivating these kinds of children seems to be very difficult. The level of self-esteem is low in children and because of that, it's difficult to motivate the child. Sometimes they feel hard when the children have emotional issues, and this affects their performance. Sometimes they suddenly have mood swings and they can't understand what to do.

But then, during moments when learners with special educational needs experience tantrums, most of the respondents agreed and found effortless to redirect the focus towards engaging activities such as gardening or farming, or even reviewing the notebooks of other learners. This could also allow them to effectively manage the situation but also ensure that they maintain a productive and nurturing learning environment. It is therefore expected that teachers in inclusive classrooms provide differentiated instruction for students who receive special education services and share their classroom with special education teachers (Afolabi, 2015).

It is challenging to plan lessons around the pullout time because of the nature of the teachers' schedules, especially when a teacher has a couple of students with disabilities who receive different related services at different times. realized that students who are pulled out for related services have limited access to the layered process of digital reading assignments or projects that could show their creative abilities. This is one of the challenges that inclusion teachers face (Afolabi, 2015).

Table 3. *Teacher Struggles in Learners with Special Needs Education*

Indicators	Mean	±	SD	Description
1. I have difficulty facilitating the lessons at school with the learners having mental disabilities.	2.71	±	0.80	Agree
2. Having a hard time giving instructions/facilitating learners with special education.	2.73	±	0.75	Agree
3. The workload of having learners with special education is too heavy for me to facilitate and give my day a success.	2.61	±	0.81	Agree
4. I easily facilitate learners with special needs education having tantrums in the classroom/house because of little knowledge of the guidance service.	2.54	±	0.72	Agree
5. My facilitation in the classroom/house has weaned my enthusiasm for facilitating their learning.	2.80	±	0.67	Agree
6. Their trouble in class/home is what makes me weak in teaching them	2.47	±	0.96	Disagree
Weighted Mean	2.64	±	0.54	Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of the extent of challenges by the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms in terms of teacher struggles in learners with special needs education. The total measure of respondents' struggles in teaching learners with special needs was 2.64, indicating that the respondents had an overall agreement on the statements.

The first statement in the table, "Teachers have difficulty facilitating the lessons at school with the learners having mental disabilities," revealed 2.71 as the average and 0.75 as the standard deviation, indicating that the teachers agreed with the statement. The second and third statements, "Having a hard time giving instructions/facilitating learners with special education" and "the workload of having learners with special education is too heavy for me to facilitate and give my day a success," received mean scores of 2.73 and 3.52, while the third statement received mean scores of 2.81 and 0.81, indicating that the teachers agreed that they had a hard time in facilitating/teaching learners with special needs as most of these teachers didn't have any background in facilitating special education. The fourth statement, "I easily facilitate learners with special needs education having tantrums in the classroom/house as they also had little knowledge of the guidance service," revealed a standard deviation of 0.71 and a mean score of 2.54, indicating that teachers agreed with facilitating learners with special needs education having tantrums in the classroom/house as they also had little knowledge of the guidance service. Furthermore, the remaining statement "My facilitation in the classroom/house has weaned my enthusiasm for facilitating their learning," received a mean score of 2.80 and a standard deviation of 0.67, indicating that the teachers had no passion for facilitating learning. The last statement, "their trouble in class/home is what makes me weak in teaching them", revealed a mean score of 2.47 and a standard deviation of 0.96, indicating that teachers disagreed that even if there were some troubles in the class, this would not stop them in teaching learners with special needs.

The result showed tough times in dealing with learners such as these. Most of the respondents agreed that they had difficulty in facilitating the lessons at school with the learners having mental disabilities. They also had a hard time giving instructions/facilitating learners with special education. They couldn't facilitate learners with special needs in education when having tantrums in the classroom/house because teachers have little knowledge of the guidance services. As a result, they could have had an unproductive and teachers could be less motivated in teaching these learners. Even having learners with special education is a workload and too heavy

for them to facilitate they still find it challenging and rewarding.

One important thing to consider is how qualified the teachers are to teach in such diverse classrooms. Highly qualified teachers are expected to teach students with disabilities (U. S. Department of Education) in inclusive classrooms. High teachers' self-efficacy is a key ingredient in creating "successful inclusive classroom environments", which therefore means that if teachers' perceived efficacy is low, it affects the teaching and learning in the classroom. When teachers are knowledgeable about a program, they have confidence in implementing it. Therefore, teachers' understanding of co-teaching models helps them to implement them well to meet the needs of students with disabilities in their classrooms. Therefore, teachers of inclusive classrooms need to receive training to meet the needs of their students (Afolabi, 2018).

Table 4 shows the mean and standard deviation of the extent of challenges by the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms in terms of behavioral transformations of learners with special needs. The table includes 6 statements about the behavioral transformations of learners with special needs.

The first statement in the table, "I lost my temper when learners with disabilities had tantrums", received 2.30 as the average and 0.90 as the standard deviation, indicating that the teachers disagreed with the statement. This finding showed that respondents couldn't handle situations when there were problems for these learners.

Table 4. Behavioral Transformations of Learners with Special Needs

Indicators	Mean	±	SD	Description
1. I lost my temper when learners with disabilities had tantrums.	2.30	±	0.90	Disagree
2. I have enough knowledge in teaching children with mental disorders.	2.18	±	0.87	Disagree
3. I concentrate my teaching/facilitating instructions with learners with mental disabilities.	2.39	±	0.93	Disagree
4. I have enough time to facilitate education for learners/children with special needs because of my household chores or teaching regular learners.	2.40	±	0.93	Disagree
5. I always give importance to the regular education learners in the classroom/house.	2.78	±	0.92	Agree
6. Whenever I see learners with mental disorders, I get mad.	1.93	±	0.95	Disagree
Weighted Mean	2.33	±	0.61	Disagree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

The first statement in the table, "I lost my temper when learners with disabilities had tantrums", received 2.30 as the average and 0.90 as the standard deviation, indicating that the teachers disagreed with the statement. This finding showed that respondents couldn't handle situations when there were problems for these learners.

Another common challenge with teaching special education is dealing with the behaviors of students. Many students with disabilities get frustrated with school. Whether it is not understanding material or dealing with emotions they have trouble controlling, these students can be a challenge for their teachers (Jonesboro, 2016).

The second statement, "I have enough knowledge in teaching children with mental disorders.", received mean scores of 2.18 and 0.87 as standard deviation, indicating that respondents don't have enough knowledge in facilitating children with special needs. According to (Kurth, 2017) teachers need to be trained about the UDL features and the variety of strategies to meet the learning styles of students in the classroom). UDL features provide support to teachers' needs, for example, guiding the planning of lesson activities based on student's learning needs in reading.

The third and fourth statements, "I concentrate my teaching/facilitating instructions with learners with mental disabilities and I have enough time to facilitate education for learners/children with special needs because of my household chores or teaching regular learners.", received mean scores of 2.49 and 2.50 with a standard deviation of 0.93, indicating that respondents didn't concentrate and didn't have enough time in facilitating learners with special needs.

According to (Evans, 2015) fair treatment should also be given to all the students. Paying attention to the needs of students from within your course design including an equality analysis/impact assessment process in yourself development is a useful way of ensuring that you give due consideration to inclusivity and accessibility.

The fifth statement "I always give importance to the regular education learners in the classroom/house.", received an average of 2.78 and a standard deviation of 0.92, indicating that most respondents gave more attention to regular education learners than learners with special needs. Furthermore, the sixth statement received a mean score of 1.93 and 0.95 as standard deviation. This score means that respondents they still understood the need to help the learners with special needs.

The teachers need to understand their roles and responsibilities in implementing the support facilitation inclusive model. According to the document, "A Guide for School Site Leaders," from the Department of Education of Louisiana (Kilgore, 2013), one of the 10 steps to implementing effective inclusive practices is to train educators on the model of inclusion to understand their roles and responsibilities in implementing it: If inclusive practices are to be implemented appropriately, staff members must receive professional development on the models of inclusive practices and how to implement them. Without training, staff will not be able to implement inclusive practices in reasonable and appropriate ways.

Table 5 shows the mean and standard deviation of the extent of challenges by the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms in terms of assistance at school. The table includes 6 statements about respondents' reactions in terms of assistance at school.

Table 5. *Assistance at School*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I have enough knowledge to care for and give quality assistance when my child/learner got a tantrum in the school/house.	2.40	±	0.82	Disagree
2. I have a guidance and counselling expert who can help me in coping up whenever my child/learner got a tantrum.	2.43	±	0.83	Disagree
3. I'm starting to feel completely demotivated in educating the learner/child with special educational needs. Every time I attempt to provide instructions for learning, it just seems to disrupt and ruin my entire day.	2.33	±	0.88	Disagree
4. I constantly feel utterly unsupported at school when it comes to educating learners/children with special educational needs. Whenever I try to express my frustrations about the challenges, I face in facilitating their learning, there is simply no one there to offer assistance or understanding.	2.37	±	0.78	Disagree
5. I feel discouraged when instructing learners with special educational needs who face difficulties, especially when they feel intimidated by their classmates during the learning process.	2.26	±	0.83	Disagree
6. I find it overwhelmingly burdensome to manage learners with mental disabilities in a regular classroom or at home. The demands often exceed the time and resources I have available.	2.36	±	0.91	Disagree
Weighted Mean	2.36	±	0.68	Disagree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

The first and second statements "I have enough knowledge to care for and give quality assistance when my child/learner got a tantrum in the school/house and I have a guidance and counseling expert who can help me in coping up whenever my child/learner got a tantrum.", received mean scores of 2.40 and 2.43 with a standard deviation of 0.82 and 0.83. These scores indicated that the majority of these responded that there should be guidance and counseling experts who can help them in dealing with problems with learners with special needs.

Furthermore, all teachers need to have the knowledge and wider understanding of the minimum core elements to apply them in planning, delivering, and assessing inclusive teaching and learning and to support learners adequately with their skills in these areas with different learning needs. Developing and improving minimum core skills enables the SPED teacher to consider the best way to teach and support the development of the skills of learners with special needs. Moreover, teachers in SPED encounter difficulties if they have limited skills in handling students with special needs. the parental involvement to help their children develop their potential."

The third statement "I'm starting to feel completely demotivated in educating the learner/child with special educational needs. Every time I attempt to provide instructions for learning, it just seems to disrupt and ruin my entire day, and the fourth statement "I constantly feel utterly unsupported at school when it comes to educating learners/children with special educational needs. Whenever I try to express my frustrations about the challenges, I face in facilitating their learning, there is simply no one there to offer assistance or understanding.", received mean scores of 2.33 and 2.37 with a standard deviation of 0.88 and 0.78 indicating that schools offered and supported in the provision of facilitating learners with special needs.

The fifth statement received a mean score of 2.26 and a standard deviation of 0.83 indicating that they didn't feel any discouragement in instructing learners with special educational needs who face difficulties, especially when they feel intimidated by their classmates during the learning process.

To support regular classroom teachers and special education teachers in meeting the special needs of their students, most district school boards have professionals working closely with the school team, such as psychologists, social workers, and speech-language pathologists. The role of these professionals is to consult with school staff, and to provide direct services to students, including assessment, prevention, and intervention (Kokai, 2019)

Table 6 shows the extent of challenges by the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms in terms of assistance at home. The total measure of respondents' assistance at home in teaching learners with special needs was 2.57, indicating that the respondents had an overall agreed on the 6 statements.

Table 6. *Assistance at Home*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I have someone to help me whenever I'm having a hard time facilitating learning for learners with special needs education.	2.43	±	0.91	Disagree
2. I have a proper professional guidance service to facilitate learning for learners with special needs education to guide them properly.	2.57	±	0.89	Agree
3. I owe to myself facilitating learners with special needs education because no one in school/home has the expertise to facilitate with proper guides and services for them.	2.59	±	0.78	Agree
4. No one in school/house can help and help me to facilitate learning because both of us are learning how to deal with them as regular education learners/children.	2.56	±	0.78	Agree

5. Nobody in school/home helps me whenever I seek assistance to help them pacify in their learning activities.	2.57	±	0.85	Agree
6. I am not a professional guidance counselor or psychiatrist to deal with them.	2.71	±	0.95	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.57	±	0.62	Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

The first statement “I have someone to help me whenever I’m having a hard time facilitating learning for learners with special needs education.”, received a mean score of 2.43 and a standard deviation of 0.91 indicating that they didn’t have someone to help them whenever they had a hard time in facilitating learning for learners with special needs education. The second item received an average score of 2.57 with a standard deviation of 0.89 indicating that most of the respondents agreed with the statement “I have a proper professional guidance service to facilitate learning for learners with special needs education to guide them properly.”

The third and fourth statements “I owe to myself facilitating learners with special needs education because no one in school/home has the expertise to facilitate with proper guides and services for them and No one in school/house can help and help me to facilitate learning because both of us are learning how to deal with them as regular education learners/children.”, received mean scores of 2.59 and 2.56 with standard deviation of 0.78 which means that they were obliged to handle learners with special needs as no one could help them in this matter.

Parents are a crucial link between children and schools. The importance of a healthy and strong partnership between parents and other caregivers with teachers is a well-recognized and researched topic in education. Several studies have proven that collaboration between parents and teachers improves children’s academic achievement, work habits, social skills, and emotional well-being (Banner 2018).

Lastly, most of the respondents agreed with the fifth and sixth statements “Nobody in school/home helps me whenever I seek assistance to help them pacify in their learning activities and I am not a professional guidance counselor or psychiatrist to deal with them.”, with mean scores of 2.57 and 2.71, and standard deviation of 0.85 and 0.95. These scores showed that at home no one could professionally help them in facilitating learners with special needs. This finding suggests that both teachers and parents should be knowledgeable enough about this matter.

Parents and guardians have a more complete understanding of a child’s physical, social, developmental, and family history. They are the only adults in the educational process who have been and will be deeply involved throughout the child’s school career. That continuity is very valuable. Parents may not be educators themselves, but they bring their years of experience in other professions and aspects of life to the process, along with their experience with their children (Logsdon, 2022).

The reality of having so many different placement and support delivery options can make it challenging for parents to navigate the school system, and to advocate for their child’s needs! There truly is no one inherently superior support style. The method of delivering support truly depends on each child’s needs. Some children would excel in a full-time special education class to receive the most intensive remediation and support. For some students, the social ramifications of being withdrawn for small-group resource time are significant. A child like this may prefer more subtle support, such as in-class resource support (Kokai, 2019).

Problem 2: What is the coping mechanism of the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms?

Table 7 shows the mean and standard deviation of the coping mechanism of the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms. The table includes 10 statements about respondents’ reactions in terms of assistance at school. The total measure of respondents’ coping mechanisms of the respondents in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms was 3.18, indicating that the respondents had an overall agreement with the statements.

The result showed that respondents agreed to conduct regular open forums or on teaching techniques to address and cope with the learner’s needs, they say that adjusting approaches are very relevant. They want to attend a series of training to cope with problems when they occur.

General education and special education teachers felt they needed PD on the inclusion model used in the school and other topics about teaching reading comprehension strategies, academic vocabulary, and understanding how to use accommodations for students with disabilities. Participants also indicated the need for PD that may help provide intervention tips or strategies to help minimize students’ frustrations and outbursts that may disrupt instruction. Both special education and general education teachers need training to support students with disabilities in comprehension, vocabulary, and strategies that will help the students be successful thereby closing the educational gap that exists between them and their peers (Afolabi, 2018).

According to (Hawsawi, 2002), the knowledge and skills of teachers, the appropriate use of behavioral interventions, and an appropriately designed curriculum are all fundamental to the success of students with these difficulties. Generalizing a universally applicable strategy is difficult given the previously stated variations among children with SEN in general and I/D in particular, other than to underline the importance of creating and implementing an Individual Education Plan (IEP) to ensure that instruction and curriculum design meet the needs of particular students. Thus, one of the most effective learning strategies is one based on individual learning which a teacher can employ in the planning of educational procedures to meet the difficulties faced by students with intellectual disabilities.

Table 7. *Coping Mechanism*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Define achievable learning objectives for each student, considering their abilities and areas of improvement.	3.05	±	0.68	Agree
2. Adapt the curriculum to suit individual learning styles and pace, ensuring content is accessible and engaging.	3.18	±	0.57	Agree
3. Incorporate a variety of sensory experiences (visual, auditory, kinesthetic) to enhance comprehension and retention of information.	3.11	±	0.60	Agree
4. Provide diverse and inclusive learning materials that cater to different learning modalities.	3.11	±	0.61	Agree
5. Integrate technology tools or devices that support learning and communication for students with special needs.	3.19	±	0.57	Agree
6. Implement regular assessments to monitor individual progress and make necessary adjustments to the teaching approach.	3.16	±	0.56	Agree
7. Establish clear behavior management techniques and positive reinforcement systems to address challenging behaviors.	3.24	±	0.51	Agree
8. Foster open channels of communication to address emotional needs and provide a safe space for students to express themselves.	3.26	±	0.54	Strongly Agree
9. Arrange seating to accommodate individual needs, ensuring comfort and accessibility.	3.21	±	0.59	Agree
10. Engage in regular reflection on teaching strategies and their impact on individual students, adjusting approaches as necessary.	3.25	±	0.52	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.18	±	0.46	Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree; 1.75-2.49 Disagree; 2.50-3.24 Agree; 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' coping mechanism and the challenges of teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms?

Table 8. *Relationship Respondents' Coping Mechanism and Challenges*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Coping Mechanism</i>		<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>		
Concentration factor on teaching facilitation	0.257***	<0.001	Significant	Reject H ₀
Teacher struggles in learners with special needs	0.256***	0.002	Significant	Reject H ₀
Behavioral transformations of learners with special needs	0.110 ^{ns}	0.181	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Assistance at school	0.326***	<0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Assistance at home	0.323***	<0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

Note: 1 – based on Pearson's Correlation ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$ ns - $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$

Table 8 displays the relationship between the relationship between respondents' coping mechanisms and the challenges of teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms. The result showed that the respondents' coping mechanisms had a significant relationship with the challenges of teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms in terms of concentration factor on teaching facilitation, teacher struggles in learners with special needs, assistance at school, and assistance at home. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' coping mechanism and the classroom management skills in terms of behavioral transformations of learners with special needs, was not rejected, while the concentration factor on teaching facilitation, teacher struggles in learners with special needs, assistance at school, and assistance at home was rejected.

Some parents of special needs children are disinterested in the welfare of their children and fail to provide them with adequate care. Alternatively, they may be overly protective. Both can be problematic for the child and their teacher. Disinterested parents may be involved with their child's education or interaction with their teachers, whereas overprotective parents may have unrealistic expectations from the child and the child's teachers. Both attitudes can shape children in negative ways. Parental disinterest may make special needs students less motivated and overprotective parents often diminish their child's confidence and make it harder for them to learn.

Special needs and general classroom teachers can use several coping strategies to offset stress in school. The stressors cannot be removed from the teaching environment, which is why teachers should learn strategies and techniques to manage them and maintain teaching and personal effectiveness. A simple ABC (Activating event, Beliefs, Consequences) stress management model comprising three steps for consideration: first, understanding the main causes of stress and its likely consequences; second, changing the behavior that leads to stress; third, improving teacher-student interaction and social interaction with parents and other school colleagues. Given that teaching is full of challenges, it is plain that teachers and administrators should be proactive and initiate effective change strategies. A raft of strategies should be developed, including personal stress management, cognitive-behavioral techniques, and ways to introduce flexibility into education (Kebbi, 2018).

Problem 4: Which of the classroom management skills and the work efficacy of the respondents best predict teachers’ performance?

Table 9. Variables that best predict Teachers’ Performance

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.372	0.198		11.953	0.000
Concentration factor on teaching facilitation	0.100	0.077	0.140	1.304	0.194
Teacher struggles in learners with special needs	0.084	0.106	0.099	0.798	0.426
Behavioral transformations of learners with special needs	-0.034	0.082	-0.045	-0.416	0.678
Assistance at school	-0.069	0.072	-0.101	-0.948	0.345
Assistance at home	0.220	0.069	0.294	3.201	0.002
R = 0.375 R ² = 0.140		F = 4.705		Sig. = 0.001	

Table 9 presents the variables that best predict respondents’ coping mechanisms. The respondents’ coping mechanism was affected by the assistance at home. This implied that among the variables, only the assistance at home affected the respondents’ coping mechanisms.

The R2 value of 0.375 implies that 37.5% of the variance in teaching performance can be explained by assistance at home. Hence, 62.5% of the respondents’ coping mechanism difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis is significant, with an F-value of 4.705 with a corresponding p-value of 0.001. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents’ coping mechanism, was not rejected in terms of assistance at home.

As for the rest of the external coping strategies, they were related to friends, family, and other people who were not related to the school. Interestingly, the majority of the coping strategies that were deemed “extremely effective” were categorized as “internal”. Among the “extremely effective” coping strategies, “Organizing your time and setting priorities” corresponded to what we previously identified as the main sources of stress namely: “Demands on after-school time” and “Too much work to do”. In the researchers’ opinion, most teachers dealing with students with special needs were stressed because they lacked time to fulfill their duties; this explains why time management and setting priorities were effective ways to release stress. As a result, it was clear that teachers were controlling their stress by using different coping strategies to a certain extent. Therefore, schools and teachers themselves should help to develop improved coping strategies and find different ways of using them. They could apply the recommendations below, which might help to reduce the level of stress that teachers encounter daily at school (Kebbi, 2018).

According to, Parent and guardian participation in the special education decision-making process is vitally important. The most important thing parents of disabled kids can do is take an active role as a member of the Individual Education Program (IEP) team that determines a student's path. The IEP team is charged with making educational decisions for students and addresses issues such as eligibility, evaluation, program development, and placement of a child in special education or gifted programs.1 Parents and guardians know their kids better and should be very involved in the IEP process.

Problem 5: What action plan can be designed based on the findings of the study?

Teachers regularly have to manage many workloads. Thus, they can easily put things in when dealing with learners with special needs. On the other hand, it is important that teachers have to seek help from the people around him/her.

Activities for teachers’ knowledge about inclusive education should be ongoing and all-encompassing. Engaging oneself in training, seminars, and socializing with friends can help improve knowledge about special education facilitation.

The knowledge of and access to institutional support networks, such as employee assistance programs, should go hand in hand with these activities. Positive effects on teacher's and other school staff members' knowledge would also result from supportive and trustworthy workplace cultures and learners’ benefits. The head of the school can set up programs, provide resources and publications, and promote staff interactions at work about inclusive education.

ACTION PLAN ON INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Key Action Steps/Strategies to Achieve Objective	Persons Responsible	Activities	Resources/Budget Needed	Date of Completion	Threats/Potential Barriers	Indicators of Success
To promote inclusive education among learners through creating guidance and counselling corner in every classroom.	Principal, Teachers, and Learners	Reproducing of printed reading materials or pictures about inclusive education.	MODE	August 2024	-Unavailability of the Experts/Speakers -Unavailability of funds to conduct the seminar.	List Peer Facilitators Circle
To establish Peer Facilitators Circle	Principals and	List Peer Facilitators Circle		September 2024		Peer Facilitators

To reproduce/replicate teaching aids, modules, and developmental instructional materials	Teachers	PeerFacilitators Circle Projects and Plans Reproducing/ replicating teaching aids and other IMS about Inclusive Education	December 2024	Circle Projects and Plan Increased active participation and understanding about Inclusive Education
To conduct Symposium among parents and stakeholders about Inclusive Education,	Principals, Teachers, Parents, and Barangay Officials	School symposium of seminar for parents and stakeholders about Inclusive Education		

Conclusion

Findings revealed that there should be a provision of Special Education Teachers in each school and schools also provide enough resources to facilitate learners with special needs. It also found that there was a lack of support from the parents of these learners with special needs as both teachers and parents don't have enough knowledge in handling/facilitating these learners. The only challenge for teachers in teaching learners with special needs in regular education classrooms was the assistance at home. It had a high effect on teacher's coping mechanisms that if left neglected, there was a tendency to affect teaching performances.

Based on the findings and conclusions made in the study, the following recommendations were drawn. (1) It is recommended that teachers should attend seminars and training on Special and Inclusive Education; (2) Parents and the community should pay attention to their children's behavior to help the teachers facilitation learners with special needs; (3) Curriculum planners should support the educational goals of Basic Education in the country by conducting Special and Inclusive Education; (4) School administrators should support and have a trusting workplace culture to have a positive impact on the teaching and learning process, and (5) It is recommended that future researchers should expand the findings of the study and utilize other variables related to Special and Inclusive Education.

References

- Afolabi, D. (2015). Elementary teachers' perspectives of the support facilitation instructional model. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=7097&context=dissertations>
- Agai-Demjaha, T (2015). Level of work related stress among teachers in elementary schools. open access macedonian journal of medical sciences 3(3):484 <https://DOI:10.3889/oamjms.2015.076>
- Ancio, E (2018). Special education teacher stress: coping strategies. education and treatment of children. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328279739_Special_Education_Teacher_Stress_Coping_Strategies
- Bandura, A. (1986). Social cognitive theory.
- Banner, T. (2018). Parent-teacher partnerships. <https://www.varkeyfoundation.org/what-we-do/research/parent-teacher-partnerships#:~:text=%5B7%5D%20Several%20studies%20have%20proven,skills%20and%20emotional%20well%2Dbeing>
- Bettini, E. et. al.(2017). Workload Manageability Among Novice Special and General Educators: Relationships With Emotional Exhaustion and Career Intentions. *Remedial and Special Education* 38(4). DOI:10.1177/0741932517708327
- Bonanno, G. et.al. (2013). Regulatory Flexibility: An Individual Differences Perspective on Coping and Emotion Regulation. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691613504116>
- Bronfenbrenner U., & Morris, P. A. (1998). The ecology of developmental processes. In R. M. Lerner (Ed.), *Handbook of Child Psychology* (5th ed., Vol. 1, pp. 993–1028). New York: Wiley.
- Bronfenbrenner, U., & Neville, P. R. (1994). America's children and families: An international perspective. In S. L. Kagan & B. Weissbourd (Eds.), *Putting families first* (pp. 3–27). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Deci, E. & Ryan R. (2012). *Self-Determination Theory*.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. New York, NY: Plenum.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11, 227-268. DOI:10.1353/etc.2018.0025
- Department of Education (2020) Programs and projects of department of education. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp->

content/uploads/2021/10/DepEd-Programs-and-Projects-Profile_2020.pdf

- Evans, J. (2026). The single-case reporting guideline in behavioral interventions. <https://doi.org/10.2522/ptj.2016.96.7.e1>
- Forlin, C., Hattie, J., & Leyser, Y. (2017). Special education: Inclusion in international contexts. In *Handbook of International Special Education* (pp. 1-14). Routledge.
- Friend, M., & Cook, L. (2013). *Interactions: Collaboration skills for school professionals*. Pearson Higher Ed.
- Guardo, J. (2015). Women Leadership in the Mosque Líderes femininas na Mesquita. DOI:10.5752/P.2175-5841.2015v13n39p1427
- Hardcastle, S. (2017). Identifying content-based and relational techniques to change behaviour in motivational interviewing.
- Hendry, G. & Oliver G. (2012). Seeing is believing: the benefits of peer observation. <https://doi.org/10.53761/1.9.1.7>
- Hu, C. (2020). Understanding College Students' Perceptions of Effective Teaching. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education* 2020, Volume 32, Number 2, 318-328 <http://www.isetl.org/ijtlhe/>
- Jonesborro, K. (2016). Common challenges in teaching special education. <https://eduedify.com/common-challenges-in-teaching-special-education/#:~:text=One%20of%20the%20biggest%20challenges,order%20to%20access%20the%20curriculum.>
- Kebbi, M (2018). Stress and coping strategies used by special education and general classroom teachers. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1184086.pdf>
- Kilgore, K. (2013). Inclusive practices-making it work. <https://slideplayer.com/slide/6993665/>
- Kokai, M. (2019), How do special needs schools support students? <https://www.ourkids.net/school/special-needs-schools-support>
- Kurth, J. A., Zagona, A. L., & Enyart, M. (2017). Inclusion of students with significant disabilities in SWPBS evaluation tools [Journal Articles]. *Education and Treatment in Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26420412>
- Logsdon, A. (2022) the important role of parents in special education. <https://www.verywellfamily.com/parental-importance-special-education-2162701>
- M & L Special Needs Planning (2018). Certified financial planning for special needs families. <https://specialneedsplanning.net/>
- Mazo, G. (2015). Causes, effects of stress, and the coping mechanism of the bachelor of science in information technology students in a Philippine University. *journal of education and learning*. Vol. 9(1) pp. 71-78.
- McCurdy, M., & McVicar, A. (2019). Classroom management strategies for students with special educational needs. *International Journal of Emotional Education*, 11(2), 45-56.
- Ostovar-Nameghi S. & Sheikahmadi, M. (2016). Teacher Isolation to Teacher Collaboration: Theoretical Perspectives and Empirical Findings. <http://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/elt>
- Richard, R. (2008). The Tragic Sense of Life. <https://doi.org/10.7208/9780226712192>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55, 68-78.
- Schuck, F. & Zimmerman, B. (1989). A social cognitive view of self-regulated academic learning. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 81(3), 329– 339. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.81.3.329>.
- Sharma, U., Forlin, C., & Loreman, T. (2012). Impact of professional development on pre-service teachers' beliefs, knowledge, and practices about inclusive education. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 35(3), 194-207.
- Simininoff, E (2008). Educational Components and planning for special education. <https://open.spotify.com/artist/1oXqBoleDcmnIh5Yd8411>.
- Sprenger, J. (2011). Stress and Coping Behaviors Among Primary School Teachers. <http://hdl.handle.net/10342/3548>.
- Swain, S. (2011). Fault, Gender Politics and Family Law Reform. *Australian Journal of Politics & History* Volume 57, Issue 2 p. 207-220. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8497.2011.01592.x>.
- Tomlinson, C. A. (1999). Mapping a route toward differentiated instruction. *Educational Leadership*, 57(1), 12-16.
- Vigora-Gadot, E. (2012). The ecological footprint as an educational tool for sustainability: A case study analysis in an Israeli public high school. *International Journal of Educational Development* Volume 32, Issue 1, January 2012, Pages 193-200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2011.03.007>.
- Yeung, A. (2012). Lay misperceptions of the relationship between men's benevolent and hostile sexism.

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